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The histopathological pattern of skin cancers in Iraq

Abstract

Background: Skin cancers comprise a variety of malignancies, with varying incidence of the histopathological types worldwide. Little is known about skin cancers in Iraq. Population-based figures on skin cancers are essential for a realistic assessment of the disease burden, prevention modes and the need for caring. The aim of this paper is to present the first and the largest study of the histopathological types of skin cancers in Iraq.

Patients and methods: In the largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancers registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with the exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004) 2585 cases of skin cancers occurred in all age groups accounting for approximately 4% of all cancer cases in Iraq.

Results: The top skin cancers in Iraq were Basal cell carcinoma (BCC), Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC), melanoma, Dermatofibrosarcoma, Basosquamous carcinoma, Kaposi sarcoma. BCC is the commonest skin cancer in Iraq. There were 1111 cases of BCC accounting for 43% of all skin cancers. SCC is second most common skin cancer in Iraq. There were 904 cases of SCC accounting for 35% of all skin cancers. Melanoma is third most common skin cancer in Iraq. There were 160 cases of melanoma accounting for only 6% of all skin cancers.

Conclusion: The top skin cancers in Iraq were BCC, SCC, melanoma, Dermatofibrosarcoma, Basosquamous carcinoma, Kaposi sarcoma.

Keywords: Skin cancer-Frequency-Iraq

Introduction

Skin cancers comprise a variety of malignancies, with varying incidence of histopathological types worldwide. Little is known about skin cancer in Iraq. The incidence of skin cancers Melanoma and nonmelanoma skin cancer (NMSCs) has been reported to be rapidly increasing in some parts of the world [1, 2, 3, 4]. Population-based figures on skin cancer are essential for a realistic assessment of the disease burden, prevention modes and the need for caring. The aim of this paper is to present the first and the largest study of the histopathological types of skin cancer in Iraq.

Patients and methods

In the largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancer registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with the exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004) 2585 cases of skin cancers occurred in all age groups accounting for approximately 4% of all cancer cases in Iraq.

Results

A total of 2425 non-melanoma skin cancers were registered in all age groups; 1342 cases occurred in males and 1083 cases occurred in females. 17 cases occurred in children under 5 years of age. The average annual incidence of non-melanoma skin cancers 2.20 /100.000 population. A total of 160 of melanoma were registered in patients between the ages of 20 to 75 years; 84 cases in males occurred and 76 occurred in females. The average annual incidence of melanoma was 0.14 /100.000 population. There were 8 cases of nodular melanoma, and one case of Amelanotic melanoma.

The top skin cancers in Iraq were Basal cell carcinoma (BCC), Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC), melanoma, Dermatofibrosarcoma, Basosquamous carcinoma, Kaposi sarcoma. BCC is the commonest skin cancer in Iraq. There were 1111 cases of BCC accounting for (43%) of all skin cancers. SCC is second most common skin cancer in Iraq. There were 904 cases of SCC accounting for (35%) of all skin cancers. Melanoma is third most common skin cancer in Iraq. There were 160 cases of melanoma accounting for only (6%) of all skin cancers. Table-1 shows the percentage of various histopathologies of skin cancers. Three cancers BSC, SCC, and melanoma accounted for more than 80% of all histopathologic types as shown in figure-1.

Discussion

The incidence of skin cancers Melanoma and nonmelanoma skin cancer (NMSCs) has been reported to be rapidly increasing in some parts of the world [1, 2, 3, 4].

Histopathology	No (%)
BCC	1111(43%)
SCC	904 (35%)
Melanoma	160 (6%)
Dermatofibrosarcoma	52 (2%)
Basosquamous carcinoma	48 (1.85%)
Kaposi sarcoma	48 (1.85%)
SCS Ker type	29 (1.1%)
Epithelial tumor	24 (0.9%)
Adenocarcinoma	17 (0.66%)
Fibrous Histocytoma	12 (0.46%)
liposarcoma	8 [4 Myxoid]
Sebaceous Adenocarcinoma	6
Bowens disease	3
Eccrine Acrospiroma	2

Table (1):The percentage of various histopathologies of skin cancers.

Figure (1): Three cancers BSC, SCC, and melanoma accounted for more than 80% of all histopathologic types

The rising incidence rates of NMSC are probably caused by a combination of increased sun exposure or exposure to ultraviolet (UV) light, increased outdoor activities, changes in clothing style, increased longevity, ozone depletion, genetics and in some cases, immune

suppression. The frequency of its occurrence is closely associated with the constitutive color of the skin and depends on the geographical zone. The highest incidence rates have been reported from Queensland, Australia with 56 new cases per year per 100,000 for men and 43 for women [3, 4]. The Robert Koch Institute in Germany estimates the incidence of melanoma skin cancer as 7 cases in 100 000 person Between 1998 and 2001, Katalinic A et al reported the registration of 1784 malignant melanoma with an estimated incidence rates of 12.3 and 14.8 in 100 000 men and women.[1]. Obviously the incidence of (NMSCs) in Iraq was lower despite it's a region with high ultraviolet light exposure

Conclusion: The top skin cancers in Iraq were BCC, SCC, melanoma,

Dermatofibrosarcoma, Basosquamous carcinoma, Kaposi sarcoma.

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